

Milestone 101

Workpackage 7

Responsible Partner: ISS

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GENERAL INFORMATION

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MS 101. ROADMAP FOR THE INSTITUTIONALIZATION OF ONE HEALTH

This milestone consolidates the work undertaken in the OHEJP WP7 task 4 based on the [D7.4 “Document on the Institutionalization of One Health”](#) and on the outcomes of the workshop on the institutionalization of One Health held as a side event with the [One Health EJP stakeholders conference 2023: “Collaborating to face future One Health challenges in Europe”](#). Both events took place in the Museum of Natural Sciences in Brussels in June (19-22), 2023.

The workshop was conducted physically as an invitation-only event, with key stakeholders who took part in the One health EJP conference, in addition other participants were invited.

The workshop included participation from 57 registered, plus the PMT members of the OHEJP, so in total approximately 70 participants.

The registered participants covered a large spectrum of institutions and thus competences (Table 1) enabling a thorough discussion which covered most of the aspects related with the institutionalization of the One health at country level.

Affiliation	N. of delegates
Africa Centres for Disease Control and Prevention	1
All India Institute of medical Sciences Bhopal India	1
Animal and Plant Health Agency (UK)	1
ANSES	2
Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety - AGES	1
EC	1
EC DG AGRI	1
EFSA	1
Ethiopian public health institution	1
EuroHealthNet	1
European Commission Joint Research Centre	3
European Environment Agency	1
European Medicines Agency	1
FAO	1
Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut	1
German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) / One Health EJP	1
Global AMR R&D Hub	1
Head nurse with Acom medical services	1
Health and Digital Executive Agency	1
ICMR-National Institute of Virology	1
Institute Pasteur de Dakar	1
Istituto Superiore di Sanità	1
National Institute of Health	1
One Sustainable Health for All Foundation	1
Policy Strategy, DG Health and Food Safety, European Commission	1
PRRO	1
Quantoom Biosciences	2
Région Nouvelle-Aquitaine (FR)	1
Sciensano	3
Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna di Pisa	1
Sitra, the Finnish Innovation Fund	1
Springer Nature	1
Statens Serum Institut	3
Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark	1
University of Surrey	1
Welsh Government	1
Wildlife Conservation Society	1
World Bank	1
European Commission, DG Health and Food Safety	3
Animalhealth Europe	1
Not indicated	3
Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale	3
Wildlife Conservation Society	1
Total	57

Table 1. Affiliation of the registered participants in the workshop.

The workshop agenda (Annex 1) was divided into three main sessions, including an introductory session with a keynote speech given by Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden, who depicted a fine-grain picture of the implementation of the One Health approach in three EU Member States (presentation in Annex 3), followed by:

- a statement-driven round table with participants selected among the key persons in some EU member states that have implemented the One Health approach to a certain extent;
- a round of presentations reporting the achievements of the OHEJP that represent tools for the institutionalization of One health and
- a round table involving all the participants.

In the statement driven round table, the panellists, coming from Italy, Denmark and Sweden (see agenda in Annex 1), were asked to report on the level of implementation of the One Health approach in their countries. They were prompted to elaborate on a few statements proposed by the moderator.

The statements used for this purpose, were:

- What is your perception on the extent the OH approach is implemented in your country?
- Does it include all the sectors (public health, animal health and environmental health) and to what extent?
- In your opinion, is the OH collaboration within your country adequately funded?

- Is there an effective legal national framework for One Health implementation in your country? Or is it rather a bottom up or spontaneous process. If a national legal framework is in place, how does the connection with a supra-national framework (e.g. European) take place?
- Do you envisage that a European framework for One Health would be beneficial? Would it facilitate an easier implementation of One Health at national level?
- What are the main obstacles to One Health institutionalization (in your country)?

The objective of this session was to scan the various approaches used, in order to identify and highlight the major hindrances encountered while implementing the One Health approach, and in particular addressing public health issues.

During the discussion a few points emerged as common traits connecting the resulting level of the One Health adoption into the three countries. In particular, the lack of inclusion of the environmental sector, the absence of a legislative framework and of ad hoc investments were common features identifying major weaknesses in the three European countries. The lack of awareness of the benefits related with the use of the One Health approach, as well as of the concreteness of the proposed One Health strategy, was also identified as an obstacle in establishing an effective cross-sectoral collaboration. An additional hindrance was identified in the recognition that in some cases the cross-sectoral integration was seen by certain stakeholders as an invasion of sector-specific domains.

During the session, the plenum was also prompted to react by the moderator, who asked what keywords would characterize an ideal process of institutionalization of the One health approach.

The exercise returned an interesting picture where most of the participants converged onto terms such as collaboration, cooperation, cross-sectoral engagement, inclusivity, and comprehensiveness. The picture that emerges, is that of the generalized perception that the One Health represents a means to include all the actors needed for a comprehensive overview of the public health issues. This is in line with the broader definition that WHO gave of the term health, which would not only regard the absence of disease but includes also the welfare conditions of the individuals and their related environment. An additional important area of interest was related with trust and equity, strengthening the concept that building the trust in the One Health and in the institutions involved is pivotal for the success of the implementation of the One Health. The complete list of the keywords emerged during the workshop is reported in Annex 2.

The open discussion with the participants in the last session was directed by the moderator using the scheme reported in figure 1.

Figure 1: Scheme of the roadmap used for the open discussion session.

The discussion addressed all the points indicated in the diagram following the scheme below:

- 1) Identification and prioritization of representatives of the different sectors.
- 2) Development of a One Health plan to define the rules and the flow of information among sectors.
- 3) Facilitating and implementing cross-sectoral collaboration.
- 4) Define policies for data management and communication.
- 5) Design the most appropriate governance mechanisms.

The discussion was dynamic and engaged all the participants. As for the first two points, it was clearly expressed by the plenum that the environmental sector must be involved since the beginning in the One Health approach starting from the definition of the One Health plan. As such, the consideration of the environmental health would not be considered an addition, but rather a structural component of the One Health and thus, needs to be fully integrated. Additionally, it was proposed that other sectors must be considered already at the stage of designing the One Health approach at the country level, including those related to the social sciences in order to propose, explain and make the approach acceptable for all the stakeholders, including the civil society.

Point three of the discussion was delved into from the perspective of the many deliverables produced in the framework of the One Health EJP. As a matter of fact, the PhD project SUSTAIN, deployed in the OHEJP in connection with the WP7 work, produced a detailed description of the difficulties encountered in the implementation of One Health in pilot countries, while the different Joint Research Projects (JRPs) and Joint Integrative Projects (JIPs) have delivered a terrific number of tools to ensure that the data needed to survey, analyse, and manage the public health issues such as zoonoses, are produced in a harmonized way across sectors and are mutually shaped in a way that the cross-sectoral interoperability is ensured. This is the case, for example, of the [OH-EpiCap Tool](#), [The OHS Codex: The Knowledge Integration Platform](#) and the [Food Safety Knowledge Exchange \(FSKX\) Format](#), among many others (a collection of One Health EJP-developed tools is available in the [One Health EJP Outcome Inventory](#)).

Point four was largely discussed within the perspective of data management. The need to adopt a FAIRification process and shared ontologies emerged as a central aspect for the One Health approach to be effective both in the data sharing and the communication domains. It was clear that the development and adoption of a common Data Management Plans must be done at the very beginning of the process of One Health institutionalization, to make any policy on the data efficacious for all the stakeholders. This process needs to consider the existing legal framework, e.g. GDPR, and the legislations for national adoption.

Eventually, the need for a legal framework defining the importance of adopting the One Health approach to face complex public health issues such as zoonoses was largely shared by the participants. However, it was recognized that the process should most probably be a bottom-up approach from the country level rather than requesting to develop a framework regulation at the EU level. It has been also proposed that a promising strategy could be to introduce the need for the One Health approach into regulations related with specific issues rather than promoting general One Health framework regulations. Such strategy would also allow to find resources for installing the One Health approach more easily.

In conclusions, a schematic roadmap for the institutionalization would be defined by the “Prioritize-Design-Define-Implement-Encourage-Communicate-Advocate” axis and would have the following components:

- 1) Prioritize the sectors to be involved, with emphasis on the inclusion of environment and social sciences.
- 2) Design a plan with the rules and the responsibilities as well as the flow of information among sectors. The plan must have all the sectors prioritized involved since the very beginning.
- 3) Define a policy for the data handling. FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data is preferable over merely open data, considering that the former can be used, analysed, shared and reused

in full observation of existing rules, e.g. GDPR. Such a policy must be part of the data management plan and be developed at a very early stage of the process.

- 4) Implement the tools, for example those of the One Health EJP portfolio, to establish integrative surveillance systems, cross-sectoral data integration and analysis platforms, harmonization of diagnostic and pathogens' characterisation methods including the use of common reference materials and the aligned scheme for interlaboratory studies.
- 5) Encourage the development of education plans specifically dedicated to the One Health approach, which are interdisciplinary by nature. This would allow to train a new generation of One Health professionals with a habit of cross-sectoral understanding, collaboration, and cross-sectoral integration. Such educational plans should also include programmes for teaching the ability to communicate the One Health approach to stakeholders with a non-scientific background (e.g. civil society, policy makers). This aspect is pivotal and would also impact the following points 6 and 7.
- 6) Define the communication strategies. In this respect, the inclusion of professionals not only from all relevant science domains would greatly be beneficial when it comes to the disclosure of the One Health approach to the civil society and, more importantly, to the policy makers, for them to understand the significance of the One health and to recognize the benefits related with its adoption.
- 7) Advocate for the One Health approach to be explicitly mentioned in the relevant legislation regarding complex public health issues such as zoonoses, in order to have a national framework and to find resources for the approach to be adopted.

Annex 1 Workshop agenda

**Workshop on the Institutionalization of the One-Health
21 June 2023**

**Venue: Natural History Museum
Brussels, Belgium 21/06/2023**

Agenda		
13.00	Welcome and purposes of the workshop	Stefano Morabito/Dolores Gavier-Widén
13:10	Deliverable 7.4: Document on institutionalization of OH	Stefano Morabito
13.25	SUSTAIN: State of play on OH Institutionalization (20'+5' question time)	Sarah Humboldt
13.50	State of Play of OH Institutionalisation: Statement-driven open discussion forum	
	<i>Panellists: Henrik Ullum (Denmark), Ann Lindberg (Sweden), Myriam Sneyers (Belgium), Umberto Agrimi (Italy). All panellists will be prompted by the moderator to react to short statements on the level OH is institutionalised in their countries.</i>	Moderator Dolores Gavier Widen
14:50	Coffee Break	
15.10	Components of the Institutionalization of OH produced in the OHEJP activities	
	Capacity building, I (Knowledge, <i>Achievements of JRP</i> s). Current situation and future needs (8')	Hein Imberechts
	Capacity building, II (Resources, <i>Achievements of JIP</i> s). Current situation and future needs (8')	Karin Artursson
	Capacity building, III (Training and Education programs). Current situation and future needs (8')	Roberto La Ragione
	Science-to-policy transfer. Current situation and future needs (8')	Annemarie Käsbohrer
	Stakeholders' expectations. Input from the Stakeholder conference (8')	Ludovico Sepe
	Question time (10')	All
16:00	The missing tiles – Group Discussion (moderated)	
	<i>Roundtable discussion on the possible Items of the institutionalization domain uncovered by the OHEJP and how the roadmap document should be shaped. (1 hour)</i>	All participants
	Conclusions and proposal for the roadmap document (30')	Stefano Morabito/Dolores Gavier-Widén
17.30	Closure	

Annex 2 Complete list of keywords attributed by the plenum to an ideal OH in Europe

- Collaboration
- Communication
- Political will and commitment
- Political courage
- Data Sharing
- Trust
- Coordination
- Mainstreaming
- Understanding
- Competition
- Health for all (human animal environment)
- System thinking
- OHEJP
- Good science
- Economic advantage
- Appreciation of other disciplines
- Sustainability
- No barriers
- Co-design
- Mandate
- Anticipation
- Equilibrium between sectors
- Global perspective
- Resilience
- Research and innovation
- Equity

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Annex 3 Keynote presentation given at the introductory session by Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden

SUSTAIN: State of play on One Health Institutionalisation

WORKSHOP ON THE INSTITUTIONALISATION OF THE ONE HEALTH
SARAH HUMBOLDT-DACHROEDEN

21.06.2023

SUSTAIN

Scientific UnderStAnding of the policy process for Transboundary integration And INstitutionalisation of the One Health approach across Europe

Work Package 7: Sustainability

“WP7 explores operational means to sustain long-term research and innovation beyond the duration of the OHEJP. WP7 works on carrying out a systems analysis of the **drivers and constraints with regard to the successful institutionalisation of One Health**, which is a key precursor to sustainability.”

Research question

What are the key institutional drivers and constraints on the effective implementation of the One Health approach?

Methods – Case study

Provide insight into institutional and political structures of **Sweden** and **Italy's** public health, veterinary, environment, and food institutes.

Methods

INTERVIEW STUDY

- Target group: Experts from the public health, veterinary, food, and environment sectors
 - Working at research and government agencies
 - In Sweden & Italy
- Semi-structured, open-ended interviews
- 32 interviews
 - 13 interviews with Swedish experts
 - 19 interviews with Italian experts

SURVEY STUDY

- Target group: Experts from public health, veterinary, food, and environment sectors, working at:
 - institutes/ government agencies;
 - ministries;
 - NGOs (e.g., World Health Organization and World Organisation for Animal Health);
 - EU agencies (e.g., European Food Safety Authority, European Medicines Agency, European Environment Agency)
- Sample size: 104 participants (20 EU countries plus Norway, Switzerland and United Kingdom)

Outcome

<p>Joint Action against AMR with a One Health Perspective Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden and Chris Degeling</p>	
<p>One Health Outlook</p> <p>Translating One Health knowledge across different institutional and political contexts in Europe Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden</p> <p>One Health Outlook 5, Article number: 1 (2023) Cite this article</p>	
<p>A governance and coordination perspective - Sweden's and Italy's approaches to implementing One Health Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden</p>	

Findings

1. Cross-sector collaboration challenges
 - Mandates and priorities
2. One Health strategy
 - Problematisation
3. Meaning of One Health
 - Engagement of social & political science sector and the public

1. Cross-sector collaboration challenges

Example:
Institutes covering
water-related topics:

1. Cross-sector collaboration challenges

“Different agencies will have their different focus and sometimes that can collide. [...] And that can become a source of irritation perhaps.”

(Swedish Food Agency)

- Different mandates and priorities
 - Public health: Find source, stop contaminated food from getting into the market, protect public health
 - Food agency: Considerations for industry and economic aspects
- Create networks in “peacetime”

2. One Health strategy

“I realise that all of us are talking about One Health surveillance but none of us really knew what it was and that it was just this abstract concept.”

(Swedish Veterinary Institute)

An institutional One Health strategy

- clarifies meaning of the One Health approach,
- gives concrete goals and objectives,
- provides information on what to focus on (e.g., via stakeholder mapping, tools and networks),
- helps to clarify roles and responsibilities.

2. One Health strategy - Problematisation

One Health definition will be different for a project on AMR or Zika virus:

- different geographical location,
- different climates,
- different cultural practices,
- different population (local population, community, indigenous population, marginal groups,...),
- different stakeholders and experts,
- ...

3. Meaning of One Health

There are "different meanings of One Health"
and there is "limited understanding of the One
Health approach by policy-makers."

(Survey participants from public health institute & World
Health Organization)

- Engage social and political scientists
 - To explain social behaviours, relationships, culture, industry and consumers, political structures, organisational processes, policy decisions, ...
 - Include gender-based perspectives and indigenous knowledge

3. Meaning of One Health

- Engage public to the One Health approach
 - One Health in schools
 - Capacity building for experts and scientists

Thank you!

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